

TYPES OF TEXTS BY SPECIALTY AND THEIR USAGE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract: The article deals with the selection of texts in teaching students to read professionally-oriented texts in a foreign language. The choice of texts is made according to their professional significance for students at non-philological universities.

Key words: reading instruction, professionally-oriented reading, criteria for text material selection.

The modern interpretation of the practical knowledge of a foreign language considers a foreign language authentic text as the basis for constructing a methodology for teaching a language and developing various speech skills. It acts both as an object of observation of linguistic facts, and as a source of expanding linguistic knowledge, and as a model for reproduction, and as material for training. In accordance with the provisions of text linguistics, a text in the process of teaching includes a speech work of any length, in written or sound form, characterized by integrity and completeness in terms of the implementation of the communicative intention or communicative task of its author. In a broader sense, the text is a complex communicative unit of a higher order, a product and subject of cognitive activity.

In this regard, we can say that mastering the skills and abilities to work with it not only contributes to the solution of general educational, educational and practical tasks, but also leads to the acquisition of general communicative

competence, since a foreign language text is also an important means of self-education.

Being the main unit of education, the text performs certain functions in the process of practical mastery of a foreign language. It acts, firstly, as a standard of a speech work, which must be created in productive types of speech activity, and secondly, as a holistic speech work, which must be understood in receptive types of speech activity. In addition, the text is a source of expanding language knowledge and the basis for training language material.

Strictly speaking, each lesson in a foreign language should be practice-oriented in understanding texts. Therefore, the issue of selecting topics and types of texts used in the classroom, in accordance with the specifics of the educational institution, is not the least important for improving the practical results of learning.

Texts used in the process of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university should have a clear pragmatic attitude. With regard to professionally oriented texts, and we are dealing, as a rule, with military and scientific and technical literature, this provision acquires special significance. The pragmatism of the text, its integrity and others important characteristics are fully manifested in unadapted authentic texts, which can be widely used only at an advanced stage of learning. To prepare for work with original literature in the specialty, the teacher has to specially select texts of a certain level of complexity and, if necessary, adapt them, taking into account the preparedness of the students.[1]

At the same time, in any case, educational texts should be an analogue of authentic literature, which is read by specialists of the relevant profile. The educational text should recreate the main characteristics of the original text.

So, for example, the general construction of the text, the structural types of paragraphs used in it, the distribution of information load in them, the means of communication between them, etc., should reflect the most typical features of the

corresponding style. This will largely solve the problem of the transition of future specialists from reading adapted literature to reading the original.

It is also necessary to take into account the fact that in order to have the greatest pragmatic impact on the addressee, the authors of texts turn to a variety of paralinguistic means. The genre of scientific and technical literature, perhaps like no other, is rich in the presence of such means (drawings, diagrams etc.). It seems appropriate not to ignore these features, but to put them at the service of the educational process.

Recently, interest in non-verbal means of written communication, the information capacity and pragmatic potential of which is often higher than that of verbal means, has increased significantly, and the linguistics of the text is increasingly being transformed into the linguistics of a semiotically complicated text, i.e., a text in the structuring of which codes of different semiotic systems are involved.

In order to facilitate the process of reading a foreign-language printed text, especially a professionally oriented one, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to take into account visual means in educational texts, especially since they are standard for special literature in any language.[3]

We would like to emphasize that such a solution seems appropriate from the point of view of the psychology of perception. When perceiving the pictorial component, which, of course, is primary, readers get a general idea of the information contained in the text. When decoding the verbal component, it becomes more defined and detailed.

In other words, in the process of perception of the text, the information embedded in it is double decoded: when the concept of the image is extracted, it is superimposed on the concept of the verbal text, the interaction of the two concepts leads to creating a single common sense of the text. These perceptual actions reflect the objective, directed nature of the process of perception.

So, the subject of study of the discipline is the main lexical and grammatical phenomena of a foreign language and the rules for their functioning in statements and texts of various types. In order to optimize the process of teaching a foreign language, it seems appropriate to minimize the number of types of texts, but at the same time it is necessary to remain within the state educational standard.[2]

An analysis of the literature and the requirements of the educational standard suggests that students should know the basic patterns of constructing oral and written texts of the following types: biography; dialogic units expressing greetings, introductions, gratitude, apology, farewell, request, offer and advice; private letter; dialogue-questioning; dialogue - exchange of opinions; business letter; message; description; instructions; article; report; annotation; essay.

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